

Model Checking ω -Regular Properties with Decoupled Search – Technical Report

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Abstract. Decoupled search is a state space search method originally introduced in AI Planning. Similar to partial-order reduction methods, decoupled search exploits the independence of components to tackle the state explosion problem. Similar to symbolic representations, it does not construct the explicit state space, but sets of states are represented in a compact manner, exploiting component independence. Given the success of both partial-order reduction and symbolic representations when model checking liveness properties, our goal is to add decoupled search to the toolset of liveness checking methods. Specifically, we show how decoupled search can be applied to liveness verification for composed Büchi automata by adapting, and showing correct, a standard algorithm for detecting lassos (i.e., infinite accepting runs), namely nested depth-first search. We evaluate our approach using a prototype implementation.

1 Introduction

Model checking is a well-known problem in formal verification. Given a formal description of a system \mathcal{M} , the model checking problem is to decide whether the system satisfies a property ϕ . In contrast to safety properties, which can only express whether there exists a finite run of the system that reaches a state with certain (bad) properties, liveness properties can express good behaviours of the system that should occur repeatedly, i.e., infinite runs in which something good happens infinitely often.

In this work, we consider a liveness verification problem that arises when composing a set $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$ of *non-deterministic Büchi automata* (NBA), each with its own acceptance condition. We recall that an accepting run for a single NBA is a *lasso* $\rho_p(\rho_c)^\omega$ with a prefix ρ_p and a cycle ρ_c that visits an accepting state. For the composition of a set of NBAs into an NBA we consider the following liveness property: a composed run is accepted if there is a cycle visiting a state that is accepting for *all* components. Such a general problem captures standard liveness verification problems related to ω -regular properties. An archetypal example is automata-based LTL checking, where system components are represented as NBA and are composed with a property monitor, represented as a Büchi automaton (often the negation of an LTL property). In this case an accepting composed run witnesses a violation of a linear-time property.

The predominant approach to address such verification problems using explicit state space search is to use *nested depth-first search* (NDFS) algorithms [4, 21, 27], or *double depth-first search*, which perform on-the-fly checking of liveness properties while composing the NBAs. NDFS, like all state space search methods, suffers from the state explosion problem. Various methods, such as partial-order reduction [29, 24, 19, 9, 26], symbolic representations [2, 25], symmetry reduction [6, 22], or Petri-net unfolding [7, 8] have been proposed to alleviate the state explosion problem. Here, we add *decoupled state space search* [13], shortly *decoupled search*, as a new method for model checking liveness properties, complementary to the existing approaches. Indeed, as Gnad and Hoffmann [13, 14] have shown, decoupled search complements these techniques in the sense that there exist cases where it yields exponentially stronger reductions. It has also been shown that decoupled search can be fruitfully combined with partial-order reduction [15], symmetry reduction [18], and symbolic search [16].

Decoupled search has recently been introduced in AI planning [13], addressing goal reachability problems. Its applicability to model checking of safety properties has been shown in [11], where it was effectively introduced into the SPIN model checker [20]. However, the extension of decoupled search to cycle detection problems inherent to liveness model checking and NDFS algorithms has not yet been investigated. This paper addresses that investigation for the first time.

Decoupled search exploits the independence of system components, similar to partial-order reduction techniques, by not enumerating all interleavings of transitions across components. Similar to symbolic representations, decoupled search does not construct the explicit state space of the product. Instead, search nodes, called *decoupled states*, symbolically represent sets of states. Each decoupled state compactly represents many global states and their closure up to internal transitions of individual components. Similar to partial-order reduction or symbolic search, decoupled search can be exponentially more efficient than explicit search of the state space, as shown for reachability problems in the domains of AI planning [13] and model checking [11].

The main contribution of our paper is to extend the scope of decoupled search from safety properties, as done in [11], to liveness properties. In particular, we adapt a standard NDFS algorithm to the decoupled state representation. The resulting algorithms are able to solve the verification problem mentioned above, namely checking acceptance of composed NBAs. The main technical challenge for the correctness of our algorithms was to identify the conditions that imply existence of accepting runs in decoupled search and to show how such runs can be constructed efficiently.

We evaluate our decoupled NDFS algorithm using a prototype implementation, comparing to the well-established SPIN model checker [20] on a set of randomly generated sets of NBA and a showcase example similar to the dining philosophers problem. The results show that, like for safety properties, decoupled search can yield exponential advantages over state-of-the-art methods. In particular, its advantage grows with the degree to which components act independently of others, through internal transitions that do not affect other components.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. We start in Section 2 by recalling the necessary background on NBAs, the verification problem we consider, and a standard NDFS algorithm typically used to solve the problem. Sections 3–6 present our contribu-

tion: Section 3 formalizes decoupled search in terms of composed NBAs, Section 4 prepares the introduction of the adapted NDFS algorithm by discussing issues that would arise in a naïve attempt to (incorrectly) adapt it, Section 5 describes the adapted NDFS algorithm, and Section 6 provides its correctness proof. In Section 7 we show our experimental evaluation, whose code and models are publicly available at [12]. Section 8 concludes the paper discussing related works and future research avenues.

2 Büchi Automata, Composition and Verification

This section recalls some basic notions of Büchi automata, their composition, the verification problem we consider in this paper for such composition, and its standard algorithmic resolution based on NDFS.

Büchi Automata and Accepting Runs. We start with the definition of non-deterministic Büchi automata (NBA).

Definition 1 (Non-Deterministic Büchi Automaton). A Non-deterministic Büchi automaton \mathcal{A} is a tuple $\langle S, \rightarrow, L, s_0, A \rangle$, where S is a finite set of states, L is a finite set of transition labels, $\rightarrow \subseteq S \times L \times S$ is a transition relation, $s_0 \in S$ is an initial state, and $A \in (S \rightarrow \mathbb{B})$ is an acceptance function.

A run ρ of a NBA is an infinite sequence of states $s_0, s_1, s_2, \dots \in S^\omega$ starting from the initial state. The i -th state of a run ρ is denoted by $\rho[i]$ and we will use the same notation for other lists and sequences. A run ρ is accepting if it traverses accepting states infinitely often. Formally, $\exists j \in \mathbb{N} : A(s[j])$. We define a *trace* π of a run $\rho = s_0, s_1, s_2, \dots \in S^\omega$ as the sequence of labels $\pi = l_0, l_1, \dots \in L^\omega$ such that $\forall i \in \mathbb{N} : \langle s_i, l_i, s_{i+1} \rangle \in \rightarrow$. We will also consider *finite* runs $\rho \in S^n$ and *finite* traces $\pi \in L^n$.

As hinted in Section 1, the existence of accepting runs is interesting for several theoretical and practical reasons. On the theoretical side, the language of an NBA is the set of all words σ in L^ω for which an accepting run exists such that $\rho[i] \xrightarrow{\sigma[i]} \rho[i+1]$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. On the practical side, model checking ω -regular properties, including LTL properties, can be reduced to checking the existence of accepting runs. Such runs, indeed, provide witnesses or counterexamples for the properties of interest.

Composition of NBA. From now on we assume that the set of labels L of an NBA is partitioned into a set L_I of *internal labels* and a set L_G of *global labels*. The notion of composition we use is based on (maximal) synchronisation on global labels, in words: in every transition involving a global label, each component having the global label in its set of labels must perform a local transition, while transitions with internal labels can be performed independently. When composing NBA we assume w.l.o.g. that they do not share any internal label. Further, we assume that every global label is shared by at least two component NBA. Otherwise, such labels can be made internal. We will use the following notation: for a set $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$ of NBA, we use superscripting to denote the components of each \mathcal{A}^i , i.e., we assume $\mathcal{A}^i = \langle S^i, \rightarrow^i, L^i = L_I^i \cup L_G^i, s_0^i, A^i \rangle$.

Definition 2 (Composition of NBA). The composition of n NBA $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$, denoted by $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$, is the NBA $\langle S, \rightarrow, L, \vec{s}_0, A \rangle$, where $S = S^1 \times \dots \times S^n$, $L = \bigcup_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} L^i$, $\vec{s}_0 = (s_0^1, \dots, s_0^n)$, $A = \{(s_1, \dots, s_n) \mapsto \bigwedge_{i=1, \dots, n} A^i(s_i)\}$ and \rightarrow is the smallest set of transitions closed under the following rules for interleaving of local transitions (1) and maximal synchronization on global labels (2):

$$(1) \frac{s_i \xrightarrow{l_I} s'_i \quad l_I \in L_I^i}{(s_1, \dots, s_i, \dots, s_n) \xrightarrow{l_I} (s_1, \dots, s'_i, \dots, s_n)}$$

$$(2) \frac{\exists i \in \{1, \dots, n\} : l_G \in L_G^i \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n \mid l_G \in L_G^j\} : s_j \xrightarrow{l_G} s'_j \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n \mid l_G \notin L_G^j\} : s'_j = s_j}{(s_1, \dots, s_n) \xrightarrow{l_G} (s'_1, \dots, s'_n)}$$

As notation convention, we will denote component states simply by small case letters, e.g. s , and composed states $(s_1, \dots, s_n) \in S$ by \vec{s} , i.e., as a vector, and similar for local runs ρ (resp. traces π) and composed runs $\vec{\rho}$ (composed traces $\vec{\pi}$).

In Figure 1 we illustrate a small example of a composition of two NBA $\mathcal{A}^1, \mathcal{A}^2$. In the top of the figure, we show the local state space of the two components (\mathcal{A}^1 on the left), where the component states are $S^1 = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $S^2 = \{A, B\}$, and the labels are defined as $L_G^1 = L_G^2 = \{l_G^1, l_G^2\}$, $L_I^1 = \{l_I^1\}$, $L_I^2 = \{l_I^2\}$. A local state is accepting for \mathcal{A}^1 , so $A^1(s) = \top$, iff $s = 2$, and similar $A^2(s) = \top$ iff $s = B$. The initial states are $s_0^1 = 1$, and $s_0^2 = A$. The transitions are as shown. In the bottom, we depict the part of the state space of the composition $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \mathcal{A}^2$ reachable from $\vec{s}_0 = (1, A)$ as it would be generated by a standard DFS. Here, transitions via global labels synchronize the components, internal transitions are executed independently. The states striked out would be pruned by duplicate checking, the underlined state is accepting.

Fig. 1. Example of two NBA, \mathcal{A}^1 and \mathcal{A}^2 , and the state space of their composition $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \mathcal{A}^2$.

Verification problem and its resolution with NDFS. The verification problem we address in this paper is the existence of accepting runs in the composed NBA $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$. In words, we look for runs in $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ that infinitely often traverse states in which *all* component NBA are in an accepting state.³

³ Other acceptance conditions can be considered as discussed in Section 8.

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CheckEmptiness( $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ ):
  Stack  $\leftarrow \langle \vec{s}_0 \rangle$ 
   $V \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
   $V' \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
  DFS( $\vec{s}_0$ )
  return empty

NestedDFS( $\vec{s}$ ):
  for all  $\vec{t}$  s.t.  $\vec{s} \rightarrow \vec{t}$  do
    if  $\vec{t} \in V'$  then continue
    if  $\vec{t} \in \text{Stack}$  then report cycle
     $V' = V' \cup \{\vec{t}\}$ 
    NestedDFS( $\vec{t}$ )

DFS( $\vec{s}$ ):
   $V = V \cup \{\vec{s}\}$ 
  for all  $\vec{t}$  s.t.  $\vec{s} \rightarrow \vec{t}$  do
    if  $\vec{t} \in V$  then continue
    push(Stack,  $\vec{t}$ )
    DFS( $\vec{t}$ )
    pop(Stack)
  if  $A(\vec{s})$  then
    NestedDFS( $\vec{s}$ )
     $V' = V' \cup \{\vec{s}\}$ 

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Fig. 2. A standard NDFS algorithm for lasso search in composed NBA.

Determining the existence of accepting runs in an NBA can be boiled down to the existence of so-called *lassos*, i.e., finite sequences of states in the NBA of the form $\vec{\rho}_p \vec{\rho}_c$ where $\vec{\rho}_p$ is the prefix of the lasso and $\vec{\rho}_c$ is the cycle of the lasso, which contains at least one accepting state and closes the cycle (i.e., $\vec{\rho}_p[|\vec{\rho}_p - 1|] = \vec{\rho}_c[|\vec{\rho}_c| - 1]$). Such a finite sequence of states represents an accepting run $\vec{\rho}_p(\vec{\rho}_c)^\omega$.

Several algorithms can be used to check the existence of lassos. The predominant family of algorithms are the variants of NDFS, originally introduced in [4]. Figure 2 shows the pseudo-code for one such variant, based on NDFS as presented in [3]. The algorithm is based on an ordinary depth-first search algorithm (**DFS**) that works as usual: a set V is used to record already visited states, and recursion enforces the depth-first exploration order of the state space. Moreover, a stack *Stack* is used to keep track of the states on the current initial trace being explored. The main difference w.r.t. ordinary DFS is that a second, nested, depth-first search algorithm (**NestedDFS**) is invoked from accepting states on backtracking, i.e., after the recursive call to **DFS**. The idea is that, if this second depth-first search finds a state that is on *Stack* then it is guaranteed that a cycle has been found, which contains at least one accepting state. That is, one finds the (un)desired lasso. The algorithm is also complete: no accepting cycle is missed.

Fig. 3. Example run of **NestedDFS** starting in the accepting state $(2, B)$ of $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \mathcal{A}^2$.

In Figure 3, we illustrate the search space initiated in the accepting state $(2, B)$ that is traversed by **NestedDFS**. Once $(2, B)$ is generated again, the cycle is reported and we can construct an accepting run $\vec{\rho}_p(\vec{\rho}_c)^\omega$ with prefix $\vec{\rho}_p$ induced by the trace $l_I^1, l_G^2, l_G^1, l_I^1$ as shown in Figure 1 and cycle $\vec{\rho}_c$ induced by the trace $l_I^2, l_G^2, l_G^1, l_I^1$.

3 The Decoupled State Space for Composed NBA

As previously stated, decoupled state space search was recently developed in AI planning [13], and adapted to model checking of safety properties later on [11]. It is designed to tackle the state explosion problem inherent in search problems that result from compactly represented systems with exponentially large state spaces. In AI planning, where decoupled search was originally introduced, such systems are modelled through state variables and a set of transition rules (called “actions”). The adaptation of decoupled search to reachability checking in SPIN presented in [11] devised decoupled search for automata models, but informally only. Here, we introduce decoupled search formally for NBA models. We define the decoupled state space for composed NBA, as the result from the composition of a set of NBA.

3.1 Decoupled Composition of NBAs

In contrast to the explicit construction of the state space, where all reachable states are generated by searching over all traces of enabled transitions, decoupled search only searches over traces of global transitions, the ones that synchronize the component NBAs. In decoupled search, a *decoupled state* $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ compactly represents a set of states closed by internal steps. This is done in terms of the sequence of global labels used to reach these states, plus a set of reached states for each component. Definition 3 formalizes this through the operation *decoupled composition of NBA*, which adapts the composition operation provided in Definition 2 to decoupled state space search.

Definition 3 (Decoupled composition of NBA). *The decoupled composition of n NBA $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$, denoted by $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \dots \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \mathcal{A}^n$, is a tuple $\langle S^{\mathcal{D}}, \rightarrow_{\mathcal{D}}, L_G, s_0^{\mathcal{D}}, A^{\mathcal{D}} \rangle$ defined as follows:*

- $S^{\mathcal{D}} = L_G^* \times \mathcal{P}^+(S^1) \times \dots \times \mathcal{P}^+(S^n)$, with $\mathcal{P}^+(S) := 2^S \setminus \emptyset$.
- $s_0^{\mathcal{D}} = \langle \langle \rangle, iclose(s_0^1), \dots, iclose(s_0^n) \rangle$, with $iclose(s)$ being the set of states s' that are reachable from s in \mathcal{A}^i using only \mathcal{A}^i 's internal transitions L_I^i :
 $iclose(s) = \{s' \mid s \xrightarrow{L_I^i}^* s'\}$ and $iclose(S) = \bigcup_{s \in S} iclose(s)$.
- $A^{\mathcal{D}}(s^{\mathcal{D}}) = \forall_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} : \exists s^i \in S_i : A^i(s^i)$, where $s^{\mathcal{D}} = \langle \pi^G, S_1, \dots, S_n \rangle$.
- $\rightarrow_{\mathcal{D}}$ is the smallest set of transitions closed under the following rule:

$$\frac{l_G \in L_G \quad \forall_{i \in \{1, \dots, n\}} : S'_i = \{s'_i \mid \vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}} : \vec{s} \xrightarrow{l_G} (s'_1, \dots, s'_i, \dots, s'_n)\} \quad S'_i \neq \emptyset}{s^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G}_{\mathcal{D}} \langle \pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}})l_G, iclose(S'_1), \dots, iclose(S'_n) \rangle}$$

where, abusing notation, we write $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ if $s^{\mathcal{D}} = \langle \pi^G, S_1, \dots, S_n \rangle$ and $\vec{s} \in S_1 \times \dots \times S_n$.

In the decoupled composition $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \dots \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \mathcal{A}^n$ a decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ is defined by a tuple $\langle \pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}), s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^1], \dots, s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^n] \rangle$, consisting of the sequence of global labels $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}})$ that it was reached on, its *global trace*, and a non-empty set of component states $s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ for each \mathcal{A}^i . A decoupled state represents exponentially many *member states*,

namely all composed states $\vec{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$ such that $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^1] \times \dots \times s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^n]$. We use a superscript \mathcal{D} to denote decoupled states $s^{\mathcal{D}}$.

In explicit state search, states that have been visited before – duplicates – are pruned to avoid repeating the search effort unnecessarily. The corresponding operation in decoupled search is *dominance pruning* [13]. A newly generated decoupled state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ is pruned if there exists a previously seen decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ that *dominates* $t^{\mathcal{D}}$, i.e., where for all \mathcal{A}^i we have $s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] \supseteq t^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$. With the correctness result given below, this is safe. One can make the representation of decoupled states, and thereby also the dominance checking, more efficient by representing the state sets $s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ symbolically [17].

The initial decoupled state is obtained by closing each local state with internal steps (iclose), and decoupled transitions generate decoupled states whose local states are also closed under internal steps. This maximally preserves the decomposition afforded by the decoupled representation. Namely, as we will prove in what follows, a decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ compactly represents all explicit states that are reachable via traces that extend the global trace $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}) = l_G^1, l_G^2, \dots, l_G^k$ with local transition labels. That is, for every component \mathcal{A}^i , $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains the non-empty subset of its local states $s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] \subseteq S^i$ that can be reached with traces $\pi_i = l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n$ such that there exist indices $j_1 < j_2 < \dots < j_k$ where $l_{j_t} = \pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}})[j_t]$ for all $1 \leq t \leq k$. In words, after every global label on $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}})$, arbitrary enabled sequences of internal transitions are allowed.

We remark that the decoupled composition of a set of NBA is always deterministic. For every pair of decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ and global label l_G , there is a unique successor $t^{\mathcal{D}}$. This is easy to see, since if there is a composed state \vec{s} contained in $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ that has multiple outgoing transitions labelled with l_G , all of the composed successor states are contained in $t^{\mathcal{D}}$. This further increases the possible state space reduction compared to standard search, which needs to branch over all these successors.

3.2 Correctness of Decoupled Composition

In this section we show that decoupled search, as presented here, is sound and complete w.r.t. reachability properties. We adapt the corresponding result from AI planning [13].

We require some additional notations. We overload the set operations \subseteq, \cap for decoupled states $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ by doing them component-wise on the set of reached local states, namely $s^{\mathcal{D}} \subseteq t^{\mathcal{D}} \Leftrightarrow \forall \mathcal{A}^i : s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] \subseteq t^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$, and similar for \cap .

For a trace $\vec{\pi}$, by $\pi^G(\vec{\pi})$ we denote the subsequence of $\vec{\pi}$ that is obtained by projecting onto the global labels L_G . For a decoupled state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ that was reached from another decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$, by $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}, t^{\mathcal{D}})$ we denote the global trace, the sequence of global labels, via which $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ was reached from $s^{\mathcal{D}}$. If we omit the first argument, we refer to the trace from the initial state $s_0^{\mathcal{D}}$, so $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}) := \pi^G(s_0^{\mathcal{D}}, s^{\mathcal{D}})$.

As previously stated, the decoupled state space captures reachability of the composed system exactly. The proof is an adaptation of previous results from AI Planning [13] to composed NBA as considered here. Hence we give a proof sketch only.

Theorem 1. *A state \vec{t} of a composition of NBA $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ is reachable from a state \vec{s} via a trace $\vec{\pi}$, iff there exists a decoupled state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ in the decoupled composition $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \dots \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \mathcal{A}^n$, such that $\vec{t} \in t^{\mathcal{D}}$ and $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ via $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}, t^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(\vec{\pi})$.*

Proof (sketch). Let $\pi^G(\vec{\pi}) = l_G^1, \dots, l_G^k$, and $s_i^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G^{i+1}}_{\mathcal{D}} s_{i+1}^{\mathcal{D}}$ for all $1 \leq i < k$. We prove the claim by induction over the length of $\pi^G(\vec{\pi})$. For the base case $|\pi^G(\vec{\pi})| = 0$, the claim trivially holds, since, by the definition of $\text{iclose}()$, $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains all composed states \vec{t} that are reachable from any $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ via only internal transitions.

Assume a decoupled state $s_i^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reached from $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ via l_G^1, \dots, l_G^i . Then, by the definition of decoupled transitions and $\text{iclose}()$, the state $s_{i+1}^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains all composed states \vec{s}_{i+1} that are reachable from a state $\vec{s}_i \in s_i^{\mathcal{D}}$ via a trace $\pi^{i \rightarrow i+1}$ that consists of only internal transitions and l_G^{i+1} . By hypothesis, we can extend the traces reaching every such \vec{s}_i from a $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ by $\pi^{i \rightarrow i+1}$ and obtain a trace reaching \vec{s}_{i+1} from \vec{s} with a global sub-trace $l_G^1, \dots, l_G^i, l_G^{i+1}$.

For the other direction, if a composed state \vec{s}_i is reached in a decoupled state $s_i^{\mathcal{D}}$ and can reach a state \vec{s}_{i+1} via a trace $\pi^{i \rightarrow i+1}$ that consists of internal labels and l_G^{i+1} , then there exists a decoupled transition from $s_i^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G^{i+1}}_{\mathcal{D}} s_{i+1}^{\mathcal{D}}$ and, again by the definition of decoupled transitions and $\text{iclose}()$, $s_{i+1}^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains \vec{s}_{i+1} . By hypothesis $s_i^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reached from $s^{\mathcal{D}}$, where \vec{s}_i is reached from $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$. Thus, $s_{i+1}^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ via $l_G^1, \dots, l_G^i, l_G^{i+1}$. \square

4 Issues with a Naïve Adaptation of NDFS

We now adapt NDFS to decoupled search. We start, in the present section, by discussing the deficiencies of a naïve adaptation. Section 5 will devise a correct adaptation of NDFS to decoupled search, showing a solution to the main issue, which requires a non-trivial adaptation of the decoupled state representation. Section 6 will prove that fixed algorithm correct.

In a naïve adaptation of NDFS to decoupled search, the only thing that changes is the treatment of decoupled states, which represent *sets of composed states*, compared to single states in the standard variant. This leads to three mostly minor changes:

1. When checking whether a state has already been visited (duplicate checking) in **DFS**, we need to check dominance instead, so $\vec{t} \in V$ needs to be adapted to checking if there exists a decoupled state $r^{\mathcal{D}} \in V$ such that the new state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ is dominated by $r^{\mathcal{D}}$. Similarly for V' in **NestedDFS**.
2. Checking whether a decoupled state is accepting boils down to checking if there exists a member state $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ such that \vec{s} is accepting. Note that we can perform this test component-wise, so we do not need to enumerate all \vec{s} explicitly.
3. To see whether a state \vec{t} generated during **NestedDFS** is on the stack, in standard search $\vec{t} \in \text{Stack}$ is checked. The naïve adaptation to decoupled search is to check for non-empty intersection instead, i.e., to check whether $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains a member state of a decoupled state $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ on *Stack*. The intersection of decoupled states can be computed simply through component-wise intersection.

It turns out, however, that these adaptations are not sufficient to obtain a sound and complete emptiness checking algorithm. There are four issues, of which three can be fixed relatively easily, but the fourth one requires a substantial change to the decoupled state space in the **NestedDFS** part of the algorithm.

Issue #1. Lassos $\vec{\rho}_p(\vec{\rho}_c)^\omega$ whose cycle $\vec{\rho}_c$ is induced by internal labels will not be detected, because **NestedDFS** only considers traces via global labels. We fix this by checking for L_I -cycles in every decoupled state generated during **DFS**. To make this efficient, we precompute, for each component, the subset of accepting states that can reach themselves with only L_I -transitions. Then, during **DFS**, we just check whether there exists a component that can reach such a state and all other components have reached any accepting state; if so, we have found an accepting run.

Issue #2. Decoupled states can contain both accepting and non-accepting member states. Thus a cycle found in the naïve manner may not contain an accepting state. This can be fixed by starting **NestedDFS** from a restriction s_A^D of s^D , where each component is reduced to its accepting states only:

$$s_A^D = \langle \pi^G(s^D), \text{iclose}(\{s \in s^D[\mathcal{A}^1] \mid A^1(s)\}), \dots, \text{iclose}(\{s \in s^D[\mathcal{A}^n] \mid A^n(s)\}) \rangle$$

In words, s_A^D contains the accepting member states, and the states reachable from those using L_I -transitions via $\text{iclose}()$. Clearly, s_A^D contains *all* accepting member states of s^D , which result from any combination of local states $\{s^1 \in s^D[\mathcal{A}^1] \mid A^1(s^1)\} \times \dots \times \{s^n \in s^D[\mathcal{A}^n] \mid A^n(s^n)\}$. As $s_A^D \subseteq s^D$, all member states of s_A^D are reachable from s_0^D . Our algorithm employs this fix, in a modified form resulting from the fix to issue #4 below.

Issue #3. Revisiting a composed state in **NestedDFS** does actually not even imply a cycle. This is because reaching t^D from s^D entails only that every member state of t^D can be reached from *at least one* member state of s^D , not from all of them. Concretely, say we started **NestedDFS** from s_A^D , and reached t^D with $\vec{t} \in t^D \cap r^D$ for r^D on *Stack*. Then we know that \vec{t} can be reached from at least one $\vec{s} \in s_A^D$; and we know that \vec{s} can be reached from at least one $\vec{v} \in r^D$. It is not necessarily the case that $\vec{t} = \vec{v}$. This issue could, in principle, be fixed by including an additional cycle-check routine, that for each component individually identifies the pairwise component-state reachability relation between s_A^D and $t^D \cap r^D$, and checks whether that relation is cyclic. We do not employ that fix because it is rendered obsolete by the solution to issue #4.

Issue #4. Cycles can be *missed* due to pruning in **NestedDFS**. This is due to the same property of decoupled reachability as in issue #3, combined with the fact that dominance does not take into account *from where* states are reachable. To see the problem, say that we start **NestedDFS** from s_A^D . There may be several accepting states $\vec{s}, \vec{s}' \in s_A^D$. Say the only cycle below s_A^D goes through \vec{s} , and visits $\vec{t} \in t^D$. Then t^D might be pruned because **NestedDFS** previously visited $t^{D'}$ with $\vec{t} \in t^{D'}$. In that case, $t^{D'}$ dominates t^D in terms of what can be reached; but it may happen that \vec{t} can be reached in $t^{D'}$ only from \vec{s}' , not allowing to close the cycle.

To illustrate Issue #4, consider the example in Figure 4. The left part of the figure shows the local state space of component NBA \mathcal{A}^1 . For simplicity, we only show a single component, which is sufficient to illustrate the issue. Here, \mathcal{A}^1 is defined as follows: $S^1 = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $L_G^1 = \{l_G^1, l_G^2\}$, $L_I^1 = \{l_I^1, l_I^2, l_I^3\}$, $A^1(s) = \top$ iff $s \in \{2, 4\}$, and $s_0^1 = 1$. The transitions are as shown in the left of the figure. The decoupled search

Fig. 4. Counterexample showing that a naïve adaptation of the NDFS algorithm is incomplete. The (only) component NBA \mathcal{A}^1 is depicted on the left. The search tree on the right shows the entire reachable decoupled state space, where pruned states are striked out; the wavy arrow depicts the invocation of **NestedDFS** on the acceptance restriction $s_{0,A}^D$ of s_0^D .

space generated using NDFS is depicted in the right of the figure, where states are created in order of increasing subscripts of the decoupled states, so s_1^D, \dots, s_n^D and similar for the states $s_{i,A}^D$ in the inner search. Pruned states are striked out. Assuming that s_0^D is the accepting state from which **NestedDFS** is launched (indicated by the wavy arrow), we first restrict it to the accepting local states of \mathcal{A}^1 , so **NestedDFS** starts in $s_{0,A}^D$, where $s_{0,A}^D[\mathcal{A}^1] = \{2, 4\}$. But then, the cycle $2 \xrightarrow{l_G^1} 3 \xrightarrow{l_G^2} 2$ is not visited during the search, because the intermediate state from which it could be detected, $s_{4,A}^D$, is dominated by (actually equal to) $s_{1,A}^D$ and pruned.

In the next section, we show how to fix this, through an extended representation of decoupled states that keeps track of reachability from a set of reference states.

5 NDFS for Decoupled Search

We first introduce in Section 5.1 the key concepts in our fixed algorithm, and then introduce the algorithm itself in Section 5.2.

5.1 Reference-State Splits

The problem underlying issue #4 in Section 4 is that pruning is done regardless of the accepting states in the root node of **NestedDFS**. We now introduce an operation on decoupled states splitting them with respect to the set of reached local accepting states for each component. In our algorithm, this will serve to distinguish the different accepting states, and thus force dominance pruning to distinguish reachability from these. Formally, we define the restriction to accepting local states as a new transition with a global label l_G^A that is a self-loop for all accepting states:

Definition 4 (Acceptance-Split Transition). Let $\langle S^D, \rightarrow_D, L, s_0^D, A^D \rangle$ be the decoupled composition of $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$. Let s^D be an accepting decoupled state, and for

$1 \leq i \leq n$ let $\langle s_1^i, \dots, s_{c_i}^i \rangle \subseteq s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ be the list of reached accepting states of \mathcal{A}^i , where for all $1 \leq j \leq c_i : A^i(s_j^i) = \top$. Then the acceptance-split transition l_G^A in $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ is defined as follows:

$$\frac{A^{\mathcal{D}}(s^{\mathcal{D}}) = \top \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, j \in \{1, \dots, c_i\} : s_j^i \in s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] \wedge A^i(s_j^i) = \top}{s^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G^A} \langle \pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}), \langle iclose(s_1^1), \dots, iclose(s_{c_1}^1) \rangle, \dots, \langle iclose(s_1^n), \dots, iclose(s_{c_n}^n) \rangle \rangle}$$

The outcome state $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ of an acceptance-split transition is a split decoupled state. The states s_j^i are called the reference states of $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$.

In words, the operation splits up the single set of reached component states $s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ of \mathcal{A}^i into a list of state sets, where each such set $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_s$ contains the states that can be reached via internal transitions from the respective accepting state $s \in s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$.

As a notation convention, we will always denote split states $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ by a subscript R , and the direct outcome of an acceptance-split transition by $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$, with a subscript A .

Our search algorithm will use the acceptance-split transition to generate the root node $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ of **NestedDFS** from an accepting state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ backtracked from in **DFS**. Hence **NestedDFS** will search in the space of split decoupled states. The transitions over these behind an $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ are defined as follows:

Definition 5 (Split Transitions). Let $\langle S^{\mathcal{D}}, \rightarrow_{\mathcal{D}}, L, s_0^{\mathcal{D}}, A^{\mathcal{D}} \rangle$ be the decoupled composition of $\mathcal{A}^1, \dots, \mathcal{A}^n$. Let $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ and $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ be decoupled states, with a transition $s^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G} t^{\mathcal{D}}$. Let $\langle s_1^i, \dots, s_{c_i}^i \rangle \subseteq S^i$ be reference states for \mathcal{A}^i . Then the split transition $s_R^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G} t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ is defined as follows: $\pi^G(s_R^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}})$, $\pi^G(t_R^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(t^{\mathcal{D}})$ and for every \mathcal{A}^i and every $1 \leq j \leq c_i$ we have:

$$t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i} = \begin{cases} iclose(\{s' \in t^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] \mid \exists s \in s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i} : s \xrightarrow{l_G} s'\}) & l_G \in L_G^i \\ s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i} & l_G \notin L_G^i \end{cases}$$

We extend set operations to the split representation as follows. A split decoupled state $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ dominates a state $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$, if the reference states of $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ are a subset of those of $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ and for all reference states s_j^i we have $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i} \subseteq s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i}$. In contrast, state membership is defined in a global manner, across reference states. Namely, the set of local states of an \mathcal{A}^i reached in a split decoupled state $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ is defined as $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] := \bigcup_{1 \leq j \leq c_i} s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_j^i}$. Composed state membership is defined relative to these $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ as before.

An important property of the splitting is that it preserves reachability of member states. Concretely, for a split-transition $s_R^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G} t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ induced by a transition $s^{\mathcal{D}} \xrightarrow{l_G} t^{\mathcal{D}}$ for all \mathcal{A}^i it holds that if $s_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] = s^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$, then $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i] = t^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$.

Considering our example again, Figure 5 illustrates how, on split decoupled states, the cycle $2 \xrightarrow{l_G^1} 3 \xrightarrow{l_G^2} 2$ is not pruned. The state $s_{3,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$ is still pruned, as it contains only component states reached from state 4. In $s_{4,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$ and $s_{5,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$, the decoupled state keeps track of the traces from the origin state 2, so none of the two is pruned, since they are not subsumed by any state $s_{i,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$ (the root node $s_{1,A}^{\mathcal{D}}$ of **NestedDFS** is not yet visited).

As indicated before, in our emptiness checking algorithm we will use split decoupled states only within **NestedDFS**. The seed state $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ of **NestedDFS** will always be

1. Before generating the successors, we call **CheckLocalAccept** on each accepting decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$. This addresses issue #1 as discussed in Section 4, detecting cycles resulting from L_I -transitions, i.e., cycles that occur “within” a decoupled state. To this end, we check whether there exists a component \mathcal{A}^i for which an accepting local state s_a^i is reached that can reach itself using only internal labels L_I^i (the set of such local states can be precomputed, so that the check becomes a lookup operation). We can then construct an accepting run for the composed system by appending the L_I^i -cycle to the sequence of states that reaches s_a^i in $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ for \mathcal{A}^i . Note that it suffices if a single component moves and all other components remain in a reached accepting state.
2. Instead of doing duplicate checking, the algorithm performs dominance pruning, pruning a new decoupled state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ if all its member states have been reached in an already visited decoupled state $r^{\mathcal{D}}$.
3. As discussed in Section 5.1, when we launch **NestedDFS** at a decoupled state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$, we do so on the acceptance-split l_G^A -successor $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ of $s^{\mathcal{D}}$.

NestedDFS now starts in the acceptance-split $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$, and traverses split transitions as per Definition 5. On generation of a new state $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$, we perform dominance pruning against the decoupled states visited during all prior calls to **NestedDFS**. If in an $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ for every component \mathcal{A}^i there exists a reference state $s \in S^i$ that is reachable from itself, so $s \in t^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_s$, then we can construct a cycle. As we will show in Theorem 2, this test is guaranteed to find all cycles that start from an accepting state $\vec{s}_A \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$.

Note that we cannot check for a non-empty intersection with states $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ on *Stack*, since these are not split relative to the reference states of $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$. Thus, cf. issue #3 in Section 4, since we do not know from which local state in $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ the state in the intersection was reached, such a non-empty intersection would *not* imply a cycle. What we can do, however, is check for dominance instead, as an algorithm optimization inspired by [21]. The pseudo-code in Figure 6 does so by checking whether $t_R^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq r^{\mathcal{D}}$, where the \supseteq relation between a split vs. non-split state is simply evaluated based on the overall sets $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ vs. $r^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]$ of reached components states. If this domination relation holds true, then issue #3 is resolved because *all* $\vec{t} \in r^{\mathcal{D}}$ are then reachable from $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ – including those \vec{t} from which an accepting state $\vec{s} \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable. Lemma 1 in the next section will spell out this argument as part of our correctness proof.

Observe that splitting a decoupled state incurs an increase in the size of the state representation, as the same local state may be reached from several reference states. More importantly, as dominance pruning is weaker on split states (which after all is the purpose of the split operation) the size of the search space may increase. As shown by the example in Figure 4, though, there is no easy way around the splitting, since the algorithm has to be able to know *from which* component state the successors states are reached. Assuming a component has M accepting states, then in the worst case all local successor states that are shared between these accepting states can be visited M times across all **NestedDFS** invocations. Unless some of the decoupled states revisiting the same member state are pruned by dominance pruning, it can actually happen that the revisits multiply across the components, so the size of the decoupled state space in **NestedDFS** can potentially be exponentially larger than the standard state space. As we shall see in our experimental evaluation, typically such blow-ups do not seem to occur.

In case we want to construct a lasso, we need to store a pointer to the predecessor of each decoupled state and the label of the generating transition. With this, we can, for each component \mathcal{A}^i separately, reconstruct a trace $\vec{\pi}$ of a state $\vec{t} \in t^{\mathcal{D}}$ reached from a state $\vec{s} \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ where $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}, t^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(\vec{\pi})$. This can be done in time polynomial in the size of the component and linear in the length of $\pi^G(s^{\mathcal{D}}, t^{\mathcal{D}})$. Since the traces for all components are synchronized via $\pi^G(\vec{\pi})$, we add the required internal labels for each component in between every pair of global labels. We remark that, to decide if a lasso exists, we do not need to store any predecessor or generating label pointers.

6 Decoupled NDFS Correctness

We now show the correctness of our approach. In Lemmas 1, 2, 3, we show that if our algorithm reports a cycle, then there exists an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$. In Theorem 2, we then show that decoupled NDFS does not miss an accepting run.

Our first lemma shows the correctness of our algorithm optimization checking dominance against the stack: if **NestedDFS** generates $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ which dominates $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ on the stack, then we have found an accepting run. Lemmas 2 and 3 show the soundness of our main termination criterion, and of **CheckLocalAccept**.

Lemma 1. *Let $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ be a decoupled state on the current **DFS** Stack, and let $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ be a decoupled state generated by **NestedDFS**. If $t_R^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq r^{\mathcal{D}}$, then there exists an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$.*

Proof. Let $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ be the accepting state that is backtracked from in **DFS**, i.e., the current **NestedDFS** was invoked on its l_G^A -successor $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$.

From Theorem 1 we know that if $s_2^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from $s_1^{\mathcal{D}}$, then for every state $\vec{s}_2 \in s_2^{\mathcal{D}}$ there exists a state $\vec{s}_1 \in s_1^{\mathcal{D}}$ such that $\vec{s}_1 \xrightarrow{\vec{\pi}} \vec{s}_2$, where $\pi^G(\vec{\pi}) = \pi^G(s_1^{\mathcal{D}}, s_2^{\mathcal{D}})$.

This result also holds for decoupled states reached in **NestedDFS** from states in **DFS**. This is because the acceptance-split transition l_G^A only restricts the set of reached member states of $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ in $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$, so in particular $s_A^{\mathcal{D}} \subseteq s^{\mathcal{D}}$. Furthermore, split transitions generating states behind $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ do not affect reachability of member states of these split-decoupled states compared to their non-split counterparts.

In particular, (1) for every state $\vec{s}_2 \in s^{\mathcal{D}}$ there exists a state $\vec{s}_1 \in s_0^{\mathcal{D}}$ that reaches \vec{s}_2 on a trace $\vec{\pi}$ where $\pi^G(\vec{\pi}) = \pi^G(s_0^{\mathcal{D}}, s^{\mathcal{D}})$, which, with $s_A^{\mathcal{D}} \subseteq s^{\mathcal{D}}$ also holds for all $\vec{s}_2 \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$; and (2) for every state $\vec{t} \in t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ there exists an accepting state $\vec{s}_A \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ that reaches \vec{t} on a trace $\vec{\pi}$ where $\pi^G(\vec{\pi}) = \pi^G(s_A^{\mathcal{D}}, t_R^{\mathcal{D}})$.

Now, because $r^{\mathcal{D}}$ is on *Stack* we additionally have that every $\vec{s} \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from a $\vec{r} \in r^{\mathcal{D}}$, and, with $t_R^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq r^{\mathcal{D}}$, that every $\vec{r} \in r^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from an accepting state $\vec{s}_A \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$.

Let $pred(s_1^{\mathcal{D}}, s_2^{\mathcal{D}}, \vec{s}_2)$ be a function that, if $s_2^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reachable from $s_1^{\mathcal{D}}$ and $\vec{s}_2 \in s_2^{\mathcal{D}}$, outputs a state $\vec{s}_1 \in s_1^{\mathcal{D}}$ that reaches \vec{s}_2 via a trace $\vec{\pi}$ with $\pi^G(s_1^{\mathcal{D}}, s_2^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(\vec{\pi})$. As hinted before, such a function can be computed efficiently component-wise.

Let \vec{s}_0 be a state reached in both $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ and $r^{\mathcal{D}}$, and let $\vec{s}_1 = pred(r^{\mathcal{D}}, t_R^{\mathcal{D}}, \vec{s}_0)$ be its predecessor in $r^{\mathcal{D}}$. If $\vec{s}_1 = \vec{s}_0$, then we are done, because there exists a lasso $\vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}_A, \dots, \vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}_A$, where \vec{s}_A is an accepting state traversed in $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$. Such

an accepting state exists because all member states of a decoupled state in **NestedDFS** are reachable from an accepting state in s_A^D .

If $\vec{s}_1 \neq \vec{s}_0$, then we iterate and set $\vec{s}_i = \text{pred}(r^D, t_R^D, \vec{s}_{i-1})$, where such \vec{s}_i exist because $r^D \subseteq t_R^D$. Because there are only finitely many states in r^D , eventually we get $\vec{s}_i = \vec{s}_j$ (where $j < i$) and there exists a lasso as follows:

First, there exists a cycle $\vec{s}_i, \dots, \vec{s}_{i-1}, \dots, \vec{s}_j = \vec{s}_i$, where between every pair of states \vec{s}_k, \vec{s}_{k-1} an accepting state $\vec{s}_{k,A}$ in s_A^D is traversed, for the same reason as before. We can obviously shift and truncate the cycle to start right after and ends in $\vec{s}_{i,A}$. The prefix of the lasso is $\vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}_{i,A}$. \square

Lemma 2. *Let t_R^D be a split decoupled state generated in **NestedDFS**. If for every component \mathcal{A}^i there exists a component state s^i such that $s^i \in t^D[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s^i}$, then there exists an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$.*

Proof. Let s_A^D be the acceptance-split decoupled state from which **NestedDFS** was started. If for every component \mathcal{A}^i such an s^i exists, then the state $\vec{s} = (s^1, \dots, s^n)$ is reachable in both s_A^D and t_R^D . By the construction of the reached state sets $t_R^D[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s^i}$, \vec{s} is reachable from itself and is accepting. Hence, there exists a lasso $\vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}, \dots, \vec{s}$. \square

Lemma 3. *Let t^D be an accepting decoupled state generated in **DFS** such that a cycle is reported by **CheckLocalAccept**(t^D), then an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ exists.*

Proof. By prerequisite, there exists an accepting member state \vec{s} of t^D . If **CheckLocalAccept**(t^D) reports a cycle, there exists a component \mathcal{A}^i , where an accepting state $s^i \in t^D[\mathcal{A}^i]$ is reached that lies on an cycle induced by transitions labelled with L_I^i . Thus, we can set the local state of \mathcal{A}^i in \vec{s} to s^i , and the lasso looks as follows: $\vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}, \dots, \vec{s}$, where on the cycle only \mathcal{A}^i moves. \square

We are now ready to prove the correctness of our decoupled NDFS algorithm.

Theorem 2. *Let $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ be the composition of n NBA and let $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \dots \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \mathcal{A}^n$ be its decoupled composition. Then **CheckEmptiness**($\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \dots \parallel_{\mathcal{D}} \mathcal{A}^n$) reports a cycle if and only if an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ exists.*

Proof. If **CheckEmptiness** reports a cycle, then by Lemmas 1, 2, and 3, which cover exactly the cases where a cycle is reported, an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$ exists.

For the other direction, assume that $\vec{\rho}$ is an accepting run for $\mathcal{A}^1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{A}^n$. Let \vec{s}_a , with $0 \leq a < k$, be the accepting state that starts the cycle of the lasso $\vec{\rho}_p = \vec{s}_0, \dots, \vec{s}_a$, $\vec{\rho}_c = \vec{s}_{a+1}, \dots, \vec{s}_k$, where $\vec{s}_a = \vec{s}_k$. Let $\vec{\pi} = l_1, \dots, l_k$ be the trace on which \vec{s}_k is reached, i.e., for all $1 \leq i < k : \langle \vec{s}_i, l_{i+1}, \vec{s}_{i+1} \rangle \in \rightarrow$.

By Theorem 1, there exists a decoupled state s^D reached in **DFS** that contains \vec{s}_a .

If $\vec{\pi}$ is such that for all $a < i \leq k : l_i \in L_I$, i.e., the cycle $\vec{\rho}_c$ is induced only by internal labels, we next proof that **CheckLocalAccept**(s^D) reports a cycle: As \vec{s}_a is accepting, s^D is accepting, too, so unless a cycle is reported before, eventually **CheckLocalAccept**(s^D) is called. If $\vec{\rho}_c$ is induced by only internal labels, then, because there cannot be any component interaction via L_I -transitions, there must exist a component

\mathcal{A}^i for which the local state s^i in \vec{s}_a reaches itself with only L_I^i -transitions. Transitions on $\vec{\rho}_c$ labelled by an element of $L_I \setminus L_I^i$ are not required for an accepting cycle. Consequently, **CheckLocalAccept**($s^{\mathcal{D}}$) reports a cycle.

We next show that, if $\vec{\pi}$ contains a global label on the cycle, i.e., there exists an $i \in \{a+1, \dots, k\}$ such that $l_i \in L_G$, then, unless a cycle is reported before, **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$) reports a cycle, where $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ is the l_G^A -successor of $s^{\mathcal{D}}$.

Assume for contradiction that this is not the case, i.e., no cycle has been reported before, and **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$) does not report a cycle. Let **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$) be the first call to **NestedDFS** that misses a cycle, although an $\vec{s}_a \in s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ that is on a cycle exists.

If \vec{s}_a is on a cycle, then by Theorem 1 there exists a decoupled state $t^{\mathcal{D}}$ reachable from $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ that also contains \vec{s}_a . The result of Theorem 1 holds in this case because, by the definition of split transitions, the splitting does not affect reachability of member states. So there exists $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ reachable from $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ that contains \vec{s}_a .

Denote by $\vec{\pi}_c = l_{a+1}, \dots, l_k$ the cycle part of $\vec{\pi}$. Because \vec{s}_a is an accepting member state of $s^{\mathcal{D}}$, all its component states s_A^i become reference states in $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$. Therefore, assuming that $\pi^G(s_A^{\mathcal{D}}, t_R^{\mathcal{D}}) = \pi^G(\vec{\pi}_c)$, for all components we have $s_A^i \in t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_A^i}$ and a cycle is reported. If this is not the case, then either (1) $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ was not reached in **DFS**, or (2) $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ was not reached in **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$).

In case (1), there must exist a state $s_P^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq s^{\mathcal{D}}$ that prunes $s^{\mathcal{D}}$. But then, $s_P^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains \vec{s}_a , too, and **NestedDFS** was called on its l_G^A -successor $s_{P,A}^{\mathcal{D}}$ and the cycle of \vec{s}_a was missed before, in contradiction. For (2), either (a) there exists a state $t_{P,R}^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ that was reached in a prior invocation of **NestedDFS** on an accepting state $s_{P,A}^{\mathcal{D}}$, or (b) a state $t_{P,R}^{\mathcal{D}} \supseteq t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ was reached in **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$) before $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$. In both cases, $t_{P,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$ is pruned and the cycle through \vec{s}_a is missed. Case (a) can only happen if $s_{P,A}^{\mathcal{D}}$ contains \vec{s}_a , too, because the reference states of $s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$ need to be a subset of the ones of $s_{P,A}^{\mathcal{D}}$. But then, the cycle of \vec{s}_a was missed before, in contradiction. For (b), if $t_R^{\mathcal{D}} \subseteq t_{P,R}^{\mathcal{D}}$, then for all \mathcal{A}^i we have $s_A^i \in t_{P,R}^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_A^i}$, so the cycle would have been reported before, in contradiction.

The reachability argument in (1,2a,2b) applies recursively to all predecessors of $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ in **DFS**, and of $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ in **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$), so, unless a cycle is reported before, eventually a state $s^{\mathcal{D}}$ is reached in **DFS** that contains \vec{s}_a , and a state $t_R^{\mathcal{D}}$ with $s_A^i \in t_R^{\mathcal{D}}[\mathcal{A}^i]_{s_A^i}$ in **NestedDFS**($s_A^{\mathcal{D}}$). \square

7 Experimental Evaluation

We implemented a prototype of decoupled NDFS, as well as the standard NDFS algorithm from Figure 2 as baseline. The input is specified in the Hanoi Omega-Automata format [1], essentially describing a set of NBA synchronized via global labels as in Definition 2. We compare our prototype to the SPIN model checker [20] (v6.5.1 from July 2020), translating each NBA to a process where NBA states are represented by state labels, internal transitions by `goto` statements, and global transitions by rendezvous channel operations. For the latter, SPIN only supports synchronization of two processes at a time, so we restrict the models to global transitions with exactly two components. The experiments were performed on a cluster of Intel E5-2660 machines running at 2.20

Fig. 7. Median runtime improvement factor (i.e., runtime ratio) of DecNDFS over SPIN (left) and NDFS (right), on randomly generated models. Shown as a function of the number of components (x -axis) and ratio of internal transitions (different curves).

GHz, with time (memory) cut-offs of 15 minutes (4 GiB). When an lasso is reported or the algorithm proved that no lasso exists within the cut-off limites, we say that the instance was *solved*. Our code and all models we used are publicly available [12].

We compare SPIN with standard options to our tool with standard search (NDFS) and with decoupled search (DecNDFS), using two kinds of benchmarks: (1) a set of random automata, where for each combination of a ratio of internal transitions in $\{0\%, 20\%, \dots, 80\%\}$, i.e., the number of transitions labelled with L_I divided by the total number of transitions, and a number of components in $\{2, \dots, 8\}$, we generated 150 sets of random graphs. Each component has 15 to 100 local states, out of which up to 3% are accepting (at least one). In PROMELA, we model acceptance explicitly using monitor process that gets into an accepting state if all processes are in a local accepting state. We ensure that none of the instances has an internal accepting cycle, to focus on more interesting cases. One could easily implement a lookup similar to **CheckLocalAccept**, which is necessary for DecNDFS, for the other methods, too, which then essentially simplifies the problem to basic reachability. Moreover, (2) we use a scaling model with ring-shaped synchronisation topology, illustrated in the bottom left of Figure 9. Each component can initially synchronize with its left or right neighbor via l_G^i or l_G^{i+1} , followed by internal transitions arranged that go back to the initial state. The accepting state is marked by a double circle.

Figure 7 shows the runtime behaviour of DecNDFS against SPIN and NDFS on the random models. The plots show the median runtime improvement factor of DecNDFS over SPIN/NDFS as a function of the number of components for a fixed ratio of internal transitions (y -values $a > 1$ indicate that DecNDFS is a -times faster than the compared algorithm). We observe that, as expected, with a higher ratio of internal transitions, the advantage of DecNDFS increases significantly. For all ratios, DecNDFS gets stronger with a higher number of components. Variance of the ratios is quite high, and there are fewer data points with 7 to 8 components as less instances are commonly solved, which explains the jumps in the plots. In Figure 8, we show more detailed runtime behaviour

Fig. 8. Scatterplot with the runtime of DecNDFS on the y -axis and the one of SPIN (left) and NDFS (right) on the x -axis, on randomly generated models. Each point represents one instance. We highlight different ratios of internal transitions with different colors/shapes.

Ratio	#	SPIN	NDFS	DecNDFS
0%	1050	347	513	319
20%	1050	376	527	462
40%	1050	390	526	573
60%	1050	420	546	723
80%	1050	461	557	888
Σ	5250	1994	2669	2965

#A	SPIN			NDFS			DecNDFS		
	Time	#States	Mem	Time	#States	Mem	Time	#S	M
2	0.01	11	129	0.00	14	8	0.00	4	8
3	0.01	42	129	0.00	51	8	0.00	5	8
4	0.01	146	129	0.00	627	8	0.00	6	8
5	0.00	281	129	0.00	3127	8	0.00	7	8
6	0.44	1762	129	0.00	2439	8	0.00	8	8
7	0.08	15663	131	0.01	10049	8	0.00	9	8
8	0.35	74455	141	0.07	42975	21	0.00	10	8
9	53.2	10M	2931	0.38	191210	82	0.00	11	8
10	1.41	336574	285	1.54	671294	281	0.00	12	8
11	-	-	-	8.13	3.2M	1523	0.00	13	8
100	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01	101	8

Fig. 9. Number of solved instances on the random models (top left), an illustration of the ring model (bottom left), and statistics on the ring model for increasing number of components (right).

in terms of scatter plots with a per-instance comparison. Each point corresponds to one instance, where the x -value is the runtime of SPIN, resp. NDFS, and the y -value is the runtime of DecNDFS, so points below the diagonal indicate an advantage of DecNDFS. Different ratios of internal labels are depicted in different colors/shapes. The plots clearly show that the performance of DecNDFS drastically improves with higher ratios.

In the left table of Figure 9, for the same benchmark set we show the number of solved instances as a function of the ratio. Here, we see that from around 20% internal transitions, DecNDFS consistently beats SPIN, for NDFS this happens at around 40%. Similar to DecNDFS, SPIN benefits from the decrease in synchronizing statements, while NDFS is less affected by lower ratios.

Somewhat surprisingly, even our standard search baseline outperforms SPIN. We conjecture that this is due to our implementation being optimized for its particular in-

put, while SPIN pays the price of the more general PROMELA input. An advantage could be the generation of successor states, which we optimized for the given type of synchronization. The never automaton in SPIN also introduces some minor overhead.

On the right of Figure 9, we show detailed statistics for the ring benchmark, with increasing number of components $\#\mathcal{A}$ (Time in seconds, #States is the sum of states visited in both DFSs, Memory in MiB). While SPIN and NDFS manage to find a lasso for up to 10, resp. 11, components, the number of decoupled states grows only linearly in the number of components, so DecNDFS can be scaled significantly higher. This showcase example only serves to illustrate an near-to-optimal case for decoupled search reductions, which likely does not carry over in this extent to real-world models.

8 Concluding Remarks and Future Work

We have presented an approach to adapt decoupled search, an AI planning technique to mitigate the state-space explosion, to the verification of liveness properties of composed NBA. Specifically, we have adapted a standard on-the-fly algorithm for checking ω -regular properties, nested depth-first search (NDFS), and proven its correctness. The necessary adaptations essentially pertain to the conditions that identify the existence of accepting runs, which must be handled differently given the different properties of decoupled states. Our approach extends the scope of decoupled search from safety properties, as done in [11], to liveness properties. Our experimental evaluation has shown that decoupled search can yield significant reductions in search effort across random models that consist of a set of synchronized NBA, and a simple scaling showcase example.

We have focused on a verification problem for composed NBAs that is general enough to cover significant cases like automata-based LTL model checking. We believe that our solution can be adapted to other verification problems for composed NBA, including Büchi automata with multiple acceptance conditions such as *generalized Büchi automata*, and language intersection of the involved automata. Indeed, NDFS has successfully been used for emptiness checking of generalized NBA. We are confident that decoupled NDFS can be adapted to the compilation introduced by [28], where an additional “counter component” is added to keep track of the components that already have an accepting cycle during the nested DFS. Concretely, we believe that the verification problem of generalized NBA can be handled with adaptations by our approach: In the compilation by [28], the counter component increases its local state from 1 to n (assuming n components), one by one whenever component i has an accepting cycle. We can essentially apply the same compilation in decoupled NDFS, restricting the set of local states of \mathcal{A}^i to the accepting ones when the counter is increased from i to $i + 1$ by a separate acceptance-split transition $l_G^{A^i}$ for each component. This ensures that a global cycle includes an accepting cycle for all components.

There are several interesting topics for future work, like the adaptation of optimizations proposed for basic NDFS (e.g. [21, 27]), or the combination with orthogonal state space reduction methods, as previously done in the context of AI planning for partial-order reduction [15], symmetry reduction [18], and symbolic search [16]. Having focused on NDFS [4, 21, 27] in this work, we believe that the adaptation of SCC-based

algorithms is a promising line of research [5, 10], extending the scope of decoupled search further to model checking of CTL properties [23].

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